

Multi-Omic Analysis of the Stage I Periodontitis Oral Microbiome: A Primary Metagenomics and Metatranscriptomics Study

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1. Introduction

The oral cavity is home to one of the most diverse and dynamic microbial communities in the human body, playing a crucial role in maintaining oral and systemic health. The Human Oral Microbiome Database (HOMD) [1] serves as a comprehensive resource cataloging the taxonomic and genomic diversity of oral microorganisms. As of the latest update, HOMD documents 774 bacterial taxa at the species level, spanning 13 phyla. The most predominant phyla in healthy individuals are *Firmicutes* (37.8%), *Proteobacteria* (30.1%), *Bacteroidetes* (17.8%), *Fusobacteria* (9.1%), and *Actinobacteria* (4.8%). Genera such as *Streptococcus* (23.5%), *Neisseria* (15.3%), and *Haemophilus* (13.2%) dominate the oral microbiome, collectively accounting for over half of the community composition. Despite this, approximately 4.8% of sequences remain unclassified at the genus level, highlighting the ongoing discovery of novel taxa.

The archaeal component of the oral microbiome is much less abundant, with only one species (*Methanobrevibacter oralis*) reliably detected and documented in HOMD. These archaea constitute less than 0.1% of the total oral prokaryotic community in most individuals, although their abundance may increase in specific niches, such as deep periodontal pockets.

The oral microbiome is not limited to bacteria and archaea; it also includes viruses, fungi, and protozoa, all of which contribute to the ecological balance and resilience of the oral ecosystem [2]. The diversity and stability of the oral microbiome are essential for the prevention of oral diseases, as a balanced community can inhibit the colonization and overgrowth of pathogenic species.

The characterization of the oral microbiome relies heavily on high-throughput sequencing of 16S rRNA genes and whole-genome metagenomics. However, there are notable challenges, including underrepresentation of archaea due to limited reference sequences and the

difficulty in cultivating certain oral taxa. As a result, ongoing improvements in sequencing technology and bioinformatics are essential for capturing the full breadth of oral microbial diversity.

1.1 Ecological Niches and Biospecimen Types

The oral cavity is a complex landscape composed of multiple distinct ecological niches, each supporting specialized microbial communities [3], [4]. These niches include hard surfaces (such as teeth), soft tissues (like the tongue, buccal mucosa, and gingiva), and the dynamic environment of saliva [3], [4]. Each region presents unique physical and chemical conditions—such as oxygen gradients, pH, and nutrient availability—that select for specific microbial assemblages [5].

Spatial Organization and Site Specialization

Recent studies confirm that oral microbes are highly specialized for individual habitats within the mouth. The “site-specialist” hypothesis posits that most oral taxa are restricted to particular niches, resulting in distinct microbial communities at each site [3], [6]. For example, the microbial composition of supragingival plaque differs markedly from that of the tongue dorsum or buccal mucosa, not only in the proportions of common taxa but also in the presence or absence of specific species [3], [4]. Closely related taxa may occupy different niches, driven by subtle environmental gradients and interspecies interactions.

Biospecimen Types for Microbiome Studies:

- **Saliva:** Saliva acts as a mixing medium, containing shed cells and microbes from all oral surfaces. It exhibits the highest intra-community diversity and the greatest overlap with other oral sites, making it a representative and temporally stable sample for oral microbiome studies [7]. However, it may dilute site-specific signals.
- **Dental Plaque:** Supragingival and subgingival plaques are biofilms formed on tooth surfaces above and below the gumline, respectively. These sites are critical for studying dental caries and periodontal diseases, as they harbor dense, structured microbial communities with unique metabolic activities.
- **Soft Tissue Swabs:** Samples from the tongue, buccal mucosa, and palate capture the microbiota of mucosal surfaces, which differ from those on hard tissues in both composition and ecological function [8].
- **Gingival Crevice Fluid:** This fluid, collected from the gingival sulcus, provides insights into the subgingival microbiome and host-microbe interactions in periodontal health and disease.

1.2 Plaque-Induced Gingivitis and Periodontitis

Plaque-induced gingivitis and periodontitis are the two principal forms of inflammatory diseases affecting the periodontium, the tissue that supports and surrounds the tooth, with dental plaque biofilm serving as the primary etiological factor in both conditions [9], [10].

Gingivitis is defined as a site-specific inflammatory condition initiated by dental plaque, presenting clinically as gingival redness, edema, and bleeding on probing (**BoP**), but crucially without evidence of periodontal attachment loss or radiographic bone loss [10], [11]. The

reversibility of gingivitis upon plaque removal distinguishes it from periodontitis, which is marked by irreversible destruction of the periodontal ligament and alveolar bone [9].

Periodontitis is a chronic, multifactorial inflammatory disease resulting from the extension of gingival inflammation into the deeper periodontal tissues, leading to the progressive destruction of the supporting structures of the teeth (periodontal ligament and alveolar bone) [12], [13]. It is initiated by bacterial plaque but involves a complex host immune response. Clinically, periodontitis is characterized by loss of clinical attachment, formation of periodontal pockets, radiographic bone loss, and, in advanced cases, tooth mobility and loss [12], [13].

Both conditions may be influenced by systemic factors such as hormonal changes, diabetes, and tobacco use, which can modify disease severity and progression [10]. The global prevalence and chronic nature of these diseases underscore their public health importance, as well as the need for accurate diagnosis, effective prevention, and long-term management strategies.

1.3 Disease Classification

The classification and diagnosis of plaque-induced gingivitis and periodontitis have evolved substantially, culminating in the 2017 World Workshop Classification system, which provides a comprehensive framework for clinical practice and research [14], [15]. Periodontal probing is an essential and routine diagnostic procedure used by dentists and dental hygienists to assess gum health. By measuring the depth of the gingival sulcus or periodontal pockets, probing establishes a clinical baseline at the initial visit and provides critical data for periodontal charting. This information is fundamental for accurately diagnosing gingivitis or periodontitis and for monitoring disease progression or response to therapy over time.

1.3.1. Periodontitis Classifications

The 2017 World Workshop redefined periodontitis as a single disease entity, replacing historical terms like "chronic" or "aggressive" [12], [13]. Diagnosis now involves staging (severity/complexity) and grading (progression rate/risk factors). Staging Criteria **Table 1**:

- Stage I (Initial): Characterized by 1–2 mm interdental clinical attachment loss (CAL), radiographic bone loss limited to the coronal third (<15% root length), no tooth loss, and probing depths (PD) ≤4 mm.
- Stage II (Moderate): Features 3–4 mm CAL, coronal bone loss (15–33%), no tooth loss, and probing depths ≤5 mm.
- Stage III (Severe): Involves ≥5 mm CAL, bone loss extending beyond the coronal third, ≤4 lost teeth, and complications like probing depths ≥6 mm, vertical bone defects, or furcation involvement.
- Stage IV (Advanced): Includes ≥5 mm CAL, extensive bone loss, ≥5 lost teeth, and severe functional impairments (e.g., masticatory dysfunction, bite collapse) requiring complex rehabilitation.

This staging framework emphasizes structural damage and functional impact, guiding tailored treatment strategies.

Table 1: Periodontitis Staging, adapted from [14].

Stage	CAL (mm)	Radiographic Bone Loss	Tooth Loss	Complexity Features
I	1-2	<15% (coronal third)	None	Max PD ≤4 mm, horizontal loss
II	3-4	15-33% (coronal third)	None	Max PD ≤5 mm, horizontal loss
III	≥5	Extends beyond 33%	≤4 teeth	PD ≥6 mm, vertical loss, furca
IV	≥5	Extends beyond 33%	≥5 teeth	Severe dysfunction, bite collapse

1.4 The oral microbiome in gingivitis and periodontitis

Oral biofilms-structured, polymicrobial communities embedded in an extracellular matrix-play a central role in the pathogenesis of gingivitis and periodontitis [16], [17]. These biofilms form on mucosal and dental surfaces, evolving from early colonizers like *Streptococcus* and *Actinomyces* species into complex ecosystems dominated by anaerobic, proteolytic bacteria [16]. In health, biofilms maintain symbiotic relationships with the host, but dysbiosis triggered by poor oral hygiene, host immune responses, or environmental factors disrupts this balance, driving inflammation and tissue destruction. Plaque accumulation at the gingival margin initiates gingivitis, characterized by reversible inflammation confined to the gingiva. If unresolved, dysbiotic shifts in biofilm composition can lead to periodontitis, marked by irreversible attachment loss, bone resorption, and periodontal pocket formation.

The etiology of periodontal disease is intrinsically linked to microbial succession within biofilms. **Socransky's color-complex theory** [18] categorizes subgingival biofilm bacteria based on their association with disease progression:

- Early colonizers: The **yellow complex** consists primarily of *Streptococcus* species which are among the first to adhere to the tooth surfaces, forming the initial foundation for biofilm development. The **green complex** consists of three *Capnocytophaga* species (*C. ochracea*, *C. sputigena*, and *C. gingivalis*), *Campylobacter concisus*, *Eikenella corrodens*, and *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans* (serotype a), which are also considered early colonizers. The **purple complex** is made up of *Veillonella parvula* and *Actinomyces odontolyticus*, while the **blue complex** includes *Actinomyces viscosus*. These early colonizers are crucial for establishing a biofilm structure that enables subsequent bacterial succession.
- Bridging species (**Orange complex**): *Fusobacterium nucleatum* and *Prevotella intermedia* facilitate coaggregation between early and late colonizers.
- Late colonizers (**Red complex**): *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Tannerella forsythia*, and *Treponema denticola* dominate in periodontitis, producing virulence factors like gingipains and leukotoxins that exacerbate tissue destruction.

The keystone-pathogen hypothesis [19] reframes periodontitis as a polymicrobial synergy, where low-abundance species like *P. gingivalis* disproportionately drive disease. *P. gingivalis* subverts host immunity by manipulating complement pathways (e.g., C5a receptor activation) and suppressing neutrophil recruitment, creating a permissive environment for dysbiosis. This enables otherwise commensal species to adopt pathogenic roles, amplifying inflammation and bone loss. Notably, *P. gingivalis* is rarely detected alone in periodontitis; its pathogenicity hinges on synergistic interactions with orange- and red-complex species, which collectively overwhelm host defenses.

Biofilm resilience further complicates treatment, as the extracellular matrix limits antimicrobial penetration, and quorum sensing enables bacterial communities to coordinate virulence expression [16], [17]. These dynamics underscore the need for biofilm-targeted therapies to restore microbial homeostasis and mitigate systemic implications, such as cardiovascular disease and diabetes, linked to periodontal pathogens.

1.5 Advances in metagenomic and metatranscriptomic analysis of periodontitis

A thorough and precise identification of periodontal microorganisms, along with an understanding of their functional activities, is fundamental to uncovering the mechanisms behind periodontitis. The advent of metagenomic and metatranscriptomic technologies has enabled comprehensive profiling of both the taxonomic composition and the functional landscape of oral microbial communities [5]. Metagenomics provides insights into which microbes and genes are present or have been present within a community, while metatranscriptomics captures the expression activity of genes, thus revealing the functional potential and real-time activity of microbial populations. [5], [20].

For instance, the review by Huang et al. (2021) [5] systematically synthesizes dynamic changes in the composition and functional activity of the periodontal microbiome across health and disease states. By integrating findings from 32 metagenomic and metatranscriptomic studies, the authors highlight consensus patterns linking oral dysbiosis not only to periodontitis but also to systemic conditions such as cardiovascular disease, rheumatoid arthritis, and diabetes mellitus.

Periodontitis is characterized by distinct metabolic shifts, including overexpression of genes involved in bacterial chemotaxis, polysaccharide biosynthesis, and fermentation ([21], [22]). While lipid metabolism is suppressed in caries, both caries and periodontitis exhibit dysregulated carbohydrate metabolism, reflecting a broader disease-associated metabolic reprogramming [23]. Inflammatory responses further reshape the microbiome, promoting virulence factor expression—such as proteases, hemolysins, and antibiotic resistance genes—that facilitate tissue invasion and immune evasion [24].

1.6 Study scope

This study aims to analyze the abundance and functional characteristics of the oral microbiome in patients with stage I periodontitis, exploring the transition phase from gingivitis to periodontitis. Samples are collected from three oral niches: gingival crevicular fluid, subgingival plaque, and supragingival plaque, with a focus on comparing these distinct microbial environments (**Figure 1**). This work is part of a larger project where patients were recruited for diverse treatment protocols.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the multi-omic approach used in this study.

2. Materials & Methods

2.1 Patients Recruitment and Interventions

This study successfully included seventeen (17) patients with stage I periodontitis who met specific inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Table 2: Inclusion criteria.

Criterion	Description
1	Stage I periodontitis caused by microbial plaque, with or without recessions, on a background of either normal or reduced periodontal support, or
2	Age between 20 and 55 years.
3	Bleeding on Probing index (BoP) \geq 30%.

Table 3: Exclusion criteria.

Criterion	Description
1	Stage II, III, or IV periodontitis.
2	Smoking of any kind within the last 6 months and throughout the study period.
3	Alcohol or drug abuse.
4	Use of antimicrobial solutions (systemically in the past month). Routine use of commercially available daily mouth rinses is permitted.
5	Use of medications affecting the gums (e.g., calcium channel blockers, antiepileptics, cyclosporine) in the past month.
6	Use of antibiotics in the past 3 months.

7	Pregnancy.
9	Diabetes, AIDS, or any systemic disease/syndrome that may affect periodontitis.

At the patient visit to the dental clinic, demographic data were recorded, clinical indices of periodontitis were measured, and oral cavity sampling was performed by the periodontist.

Demographic data collected included age, weight, height, body mass index (**BMI**), and biological sex. A periodontogram was employed to record clinical parameters such as probing depth, gingival recession, clinical attachment loss, presence or absence of bleeding on probing, plaque accumulation, and gingival bleeding. Based on these findings, the percentages for **Bleeding on Probing (BoP)**, **Gingival Bleeding Index (GBI)**, and **Plaque Index (PI)** were subsequently calculated.

2.1.1. Clinical Procedures and Sampling Protocols

Clinical indices

The clinical indices in the periodontal chart were measured in the following order: **PI** was determined by recording the presence of dental plaque using a periodontal probe along the gingival margin of each tooth. Measurements were taken at six points per tooth – three buccal (distal, middle, mesial) and three lingual (distal, middle, mesial) – excluding third molars. Results were recorded as "yes" or "no," and the final index value for each patient was calculated as the percentage of positive records out of the total.

GBI, based on the Ainamo & Bay methodology (1975), was measured by inserting the tip of a periodontal probe 1 mm into the gingival sulcus with light tension on the gum. Bleeding was recorded as positive (+) or negative (-) 15 seconds after probing, at six points per tooth, excluding third molars. The final GBI value was calculated as the percentage of bleeding occurrences out of the total observations.

The Pocket Depth was measured by inserting a periodontal probe into the gingival sulcus at six points per tooth, excluding third molars, and recording the distance from the base of the sulcus to the gingival margin. Similarly, Attachment Loss was determined by measuring the distance from the base of the sulcus to the cemento-enamel junction (CEJ), where applicable. For Recession, the distance from the CEJ to the gingival margin was recorded if the CEJ was visible and located apical to the gingival margin. If the CEJ was not visible because it was coronal to the gingival margin, recession was not recorded.

Lastly, **BoP** was assessed at six points per tooth, excluding third molars, by recording whether bleeding occurred (+) or not (-) 15 seconds after placing the probe in the gingival sulcus. The final BoP value was calculated as the percentage of bleeding occurrences out of the total observations. This measure was crucial for determining study eligibility, with patients having BoP $\geq 30\%$ qualifying for inclusion and those with BoP $< 30\%$ being excluded.

Sample Collection and Handling

Samples of gingival crevicular fluid (**GF**), subgingival plaque (**SB**), and supragingival plaque (**SP**) were collected. The samples were stored in dedicated preservation vials at room temperature for up to 30 days and then transferred to deep freezing until sequencing. The collection sequence was as follows:

1. Supragingival plaque (SP)

2. Gingival crevicular fluid (GF)
3. Subgingival plaque (SB)

SP samples were collected from the mesial of the first molars and distal of the second premolars in all quadrants, while **SB** was collected from the distal of the second premolars. If teeth were missing, the nearest interdental space was selected. **GF** was collected from the mesiobuccal regions of the first molars, with only lower samples taken.

All samples were placed in Total Nucleic Acid Preservation Tubes (CE/IVD Marked), Dx69200 by NORGEN Biotek, Canada, containing 1 ml of DNA/RNA preservative solution. Oral samples were stored for a maximum of 14 days in the periodontist's clinic at room temperature and then transferred to the biomedical biosafety level 2 (BSL2) Laboratory of Medical Microbiology, Hellenic Pasteur Institute, in their preservative solutions to retain the integrity of collected samples. To avoid repeated thawing and re-freezing, samples were aliquoted into cryotubes and immediately stored at -80°C for subsequent DNA and RNA extraction processing.

2.1.2. Laboratory protocols

DNA extraction

The QIAamp DNA Microbiome Kit (QIAGEN, Hilden, Germany) was used for all oral samples following the manufacturer's protocol for host DNA depletion and incorporating the optional FastPrep instrument at a velocity of 6.5 m/s for 45 seconds during the pathogen lysis step. For subgingival and supragingival plaque, and gingival crevicular fluid, 500 µL of each sample was transferred to a microcentrifuge tube, vortexed thoroughly, and centrifuged at 12,000 × g for 10 minutes at 4–8°C. The resulting pellets were resuspended in 500 µL of nuclease-free water, and cell lysis and protein digestion were enhanced by adding the supplied lysis buffer and 20 µL of proteinase K. The samples were then incubated at 56°C for 1 hour at 600 rpm. DNA extraction was subsequently performed according to the manufacturer's instructions, with total DNA eluted in 50 µL of nuclease-free water. For each extraction set, an extraction blank (nuclease-free H₂O) was used to ascertain potential kit and/or reagent contamination. Finally, the eluted DNA was stored at -80°C.

RNA extraction

The MagCore® triXact RNA Kit (RBC Bioscience Corp, Belgium) was used for total RNA extraction from oral samples, incorporating DNase I treatment and magnetic-particle technology via the MagCore® auto-extraction instrument. RNA extraction followed the manufacturer's protocol with modifications for specific sample types. 500 µL of each sample was transferred to a microcentrifuge tube, vortexed thoroughly, and centrifuged at 12,000 × g for 10 minutes at 4–8°C. The resulting cell pellets were resuspended in 400 µL of RB Buffer containing β-mercaptoethanol, mixed by vortexing, and treated with 20 µL of proteinase K. Samples were incubated at 60°C for 30 minutes at 600 rpm, followed by a second incubation at 90°C for 15 minutes with shaking at 600 rpm. Additional proteinase K and carrier RNA were added to the samples, and RNA isolation was completed using the manufacturer's protocol with the optional DNase I treatment. For each run, an extraction blank (nuclease-free H₂O) was used to ascertain potential kit and/or reagent contamination. Total RNA was eluted in a final volume of 60 µL. Finally, the extracted RNA was stored at -80°C.

After DNA/RNA extraction, the yield and purity of DNA/RNA were assessed by measuring absorbance ratios spectrophotometrically on a NanoDrop® ND-1000 (NanoDrop Technologies, DE, USA). The measurement includes A260/280 nm for protein contamination and A260/230 nm for salt and phenol contamination.

Sequencing

Metagenomics (DNA-Seq)

DNA libraries were prepared using the Nextera XT DNA Library Preparation Kit (Illumina), following the manufacturer's protocol for enzymatic fragmentation and adapter ligation. Sequencing was performed on the NovaSeq 6000 platform (Illumina) in paired-end (PE) mode, with read lengths of 150 bp (3 batches) and 110 bp (2 batches), to ensure comprehensive genomic coverage across heterogeneous oral microbial communities. Batch-specific adjustments were applied to optimize cluster density and sequencing depth.

Metatranscriptomics (RNA-Seq)

Total RNA underwent ribosomal RNA depletion using the QIAseq FastSelect Epidemiology Kit (Qiagen), followed by library construction with the NEBNext Ultra II Directional RNA Library Prep Kit (New England Biolabs). Notably, poly-A selection was omitted to retain prokaryotic transcripts, which lack polyadenylated tails. Sequencing was conducted on the NovaSeq 6000 in PE mode with read lengths of 150 bp (2 batches), 110 bp (1 batch), and 100 bp (1 batch), ensuring robust capture of both high- and low-abundance microbial transcripts.

2.1.3. Bioinformatics Analysis

Metagenomics Workflow

The steps, tools, and parameters of the bioinformatics pipeline for metagenomic sequencing analysis—from raw read processing to microbial identification and differential abundance—

are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 2: Bioinformatics analysis tools and parameters for the analysis of the shotgun metagenomics samples.

Preprocessing of Sequencing Data

The preprocessing of raw metagenomic sequencing data was performed using the Atropos tool, version 1.1.31 [25]. This step involved the removal of DNA adaptors added during sequencing, filtering of short reads, and trimming of low-quality bases. Specifically, the adaptor sequence CTGTCTCTTATA was removed from both the 3' and 5' ends. Reads shorter than 60 bases and bases with a Phred score below 20 were excluded to ensure high-quality reads for downstream analysis. Quality checks were performed both before and after preprocessing using FastQC (version 0.11.9) [26] and MultiQC (version 1.14) [27].

Filtering Human Sequences

Metagenomic data often contain sequencing reads from human cells present in the samples despite laboratory efforts to remove them. To exclude reads aligning to the human genome, the HISAT2 tool (version 2.1.0) [28] was used, aligning reads to the GRCh38 human genome reference (release 84). Only read pairs that failed to align uniformly to the human genome (--un-conc-gz parameter) were retained for microbial analysis.

Quantification of Microbial Species

Microbial quantification for each sample was conducted using the AGAMEMNON tool (version v0.1.0) [29]. This tool estimates microbial abundance in metagenomic/transcriptomic data efficiently, employing an expectation-maximization algorithm to compare reads against a user-provided reference database. The reference database utilized in this study was the Human Oral Microbiome Database (HOMD), Genomic Reference Sequences Version 10.1, (<https://www.homd.org/ftp/genomes/NCBI/V10.1/>) [1]. This version comprises 8,622 genomes representing 2,605 unique microbial strains, which are classified into 940 distinct species, according to the NCBI Taxonomy system. 2 of these species belong to the Archaea domain and the rest are Bacteria.

Normalization by Genome Length

Raw counts for each microbial taxon, as generated by the AGAMENON tool, were normalized to account for differences in genome length. For each genome entry in the HOMD database (identified by a GCA accession ID), the ungapped genome length was extracted from the corresponding GenBank assembly file. Since AGAMENON quantifies up to the microbial strain level, in cases where a strain was associated with multiple genome entries, the longest genome length among them was selected for normalization. Normalized taxon abundances (or counts) were then calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Taxon normalized abundance} = \text{Raw abundance} / \text{Genome length of the taxon} * 1000$$

Normalized abundances were processed in R, and the data were integrated into a phyloseq object [30] along with sample metadata and microbial taxonomy. All normalized abundance values were agglomerated at the species level, and singleton species were removed to reduce noise from rare taxa. When required, normalized abundances were further adjusted for library size using total sum scaling (TSS) to obtain relative abundances for downstream analyses.

$\text{Taxon relative abundance} = \text{normalized abundance} / \text{total normalized abundances in sample}$

Differential Abundance Analysis

Differential abundance analysis of microbial species was conducted using MaAsLin2 (v1.8.0) [31] to identify taxa whose relative abundances changed significantly across biospecimen types. Abundance values were filtered to exclude features with a minimum abundance below 0.1 in fewer than six samples. Based on the available normalization and transformation options provided by MaAsLin2, Total Sum Scaling (TSS) normalization combined with \log_2 transformation was selected, and a linear model (LM) was used for statistical testing.

The Maaslin2 function was executed with parameters: `min_abundance = 0.1`, `min_prevalence = 0.3`, `min_variance = 0.0`, `normalization = "TSS"`, `transform = "LOG"`, `analysis_method = "LM"`, and `max_significance = 0.25`. Fixed effects included sex, age, BMI, and time (days 0, 7, and 21), while patient ID and sequencing batch were modeled as random effects to account for repeated measures and technical variability.

This workflow enabled systematic identification of oral microbial species exhibiting longitudinal shifts in abundance during Chios Mastic treatments trials, controlling for demographic confounders.

Metatranscriptomics Workflow

For the analysis of shotgun metatranscriptomics samples, the preprocessing, human sequence filtering, microbial abundance estimation, and differential abundance analysis of microbial species followed the same methodology as described for metagenomic data. Prior to microbial abundance estimation, reads mapping to rRNA regions were removed using the SortMeRNA tool (version 2.1) [32], utilizing the SILVA database [33] for rRNA identification.

Functional Profiling of Metatranscriptomic Data

To identify gene pathways expressed in the shotgun metatranscriptomic samples, the HUMAnN3 tool (version 3.6) [34] was used. For this purpose, the Illumina BaseSpace Microbiome Metatranscriptomics App was used with the default parameters. This workflow takes as input the raw FASTQ files, processes reads using Trimmomatic to remove adapters,

trim low-quality bases, and discard short reads, followed by BBduk [35] to filter host contamination and residual ribosomal RNA.

The next step of the workflow is a taxonomic prescreening with MetaPhlAn 4.0 [36], which profiles the microbial community by mapping reads to clade-specific marker genes, providing species-level taxonomic assignments for bacteria, archaea, and eukaryotes. HUMAnN 3 then generates a species-specific pangenome database using MetaPhlAn's taxonomic profile. This profile identifies microbial species in the sample, and HUMAnN extracts their reference gene sequences from the ChocoPhlAn 3 database (16.8k species, 99.2k genomes) [34]. The custom database (custom_chocophlan_database.ffn) includes Species-specific coding sequences (CDS) from UniRef90-annotated genomes [37].

The custom database is indexed with bowtie2-build [38]. Reads are mapped using Bowtie2 [38] with parameters optimized for metatranscriptomic data: Seed length: 20 bp, Mismatch penalty: --mp 6,2 Read truncation: Discards reads with <36 bp post-trimming. Mapped reads are assigned to gene families, while unmapped reads proceed to translated search.

Unmapped reads are translated and aligned to the UniRef90 database (20.7 GB) using DIAMOND (v0.9) [39]. Alignment criteria: ≥90% identity, ≥80% mutual coverage. E-value threshold: 1e-5. Scoring matrix: BLOSUM62. Alignments are filtered to retain only the best hit per read, ensuring precise gene family annotation.

Gene Family abundances are computed as RPKM (Reads Per Kilobase per Million):

$$\text{RPKM} = \frac{\text{Reads mapped to gene}}{\text{Gene length (kb)} \times \text{Total mapped reads (million)}}$$
$$\text{CPM} = \frac{\text{Gene RPKM}}{\text{Total RPKM of all genes}} \times 10^6$$

These RPKM values are then converted to copies per million (CPM) by dividing each gene's RPKM by the total RPKM of all detected genes in the sample. This applies Total Sum Scaling (TSS) normalization, ensuring gene family abundances sum to 1 million per sample. Results are stratified by taxonomy (if mapped via ChocoPhlAn) or marked as unclassified (via UniRef90).

Using MetaCyc v24.0 pathway definitions [40], HUMAnN 3 infers pathway activity via MinPath [41]. Pathway abundance is computed as the sum of CPM values for all genes assigned to the pathway.

$$\text{Pathway Abundance} = \sum (\text{Gene CPM values in pathway})$$

To derive relative pathway abundance, these raw pathway sums undergo a second TSS normalization:

$$\text{Relative Pathway Abundance} = \frac{\text{Pathway CPM Sum}}{\text{Total CPM of All Pathways}}$$

This results in values representing each pathway's proportion of total community metabolic activity.

Functional Profiling of Metagenomic Data

Shotgun metagenomic DNA-seq reads were also mapped to gene families and metabolic pathways to estimate the copy number of these genes present in each sample. These metagenomic profiles were then integrated with RNA-seq-based gene expression abundances to enable differential pathway expression analysis. This combined metagenomics-metatranscriptomics approach provides a comprehensive view of both the functional potential and the active expression of microbial communities, strengthening the interpretation of pathway activity across samples.

Differential Pathways Expression Analysis

The Differential Pathways Expression Analysis was implemented to check if any pathways are differentially expressed between biospecimen types. Pathway relative abundances derived from RNA sequencing served as the input, with a negative binomial (NEGBIN) model applied after total sum scaling (TSS) normalization, using default software parameters. Data were modeled with MTXmodel (v1.2.5) [42], which is based on the MaAsLin2 statistical framework. The statistical model is fitted with:

- Fixed effects: Biospecimen type, Sex, Age, BMI
- Random effects: Patient ID, Sequencing batch (the combination of RNA and DNA sequencing batch), to account for repeated measures and technical variability.
- Covariate: DNA pathway abundance (strict RNA-DNA sample pairing)

DNA pathway relative abundances were included as **covariates** to control for differences in gene copy number, and only samples with paired RNA and DNA data were retained for analysis. Pathways present (min abundance = 0.00001) in at least 20% of samples were considered, and the data were log-transformed prior to modeling. Multiple testing correction was performed using the Benjamini-Hochberg method, with a significance threshold of $q < 0.25$. The results identified pathways whose transcriptional activity is significantly different between the biospecimen types. These findings were visualized using boxplots of pathway relative abundances, stratified by timepoint and treatment group, with model coefficients annotated on the plots to indicate the direction and magnitude of change.

3. Results

3.1 Demographics

Seventeen patients diagnosed with stage I periodontitis were included in the study (**Table 4**). Among them, seven were female. The mean age was 42.3 years, and the mean body mass index (BMI) was 26.3.

Table 4: Selected demographic data of patients.

S/N	Patient ID	Sex	Age	BMI	Periodontist
1	P1	Female	25	20.96	1
2	P2	Female	44	27.55	1
3	P3	Female	43	26.03	1
4	P4	Female	38	21.22	2
5	P5	Male	39	35.75	2
6	P6	Male	48	22.16	2
7	M1	Female	54	23.18	1
8	M3	Male	33	34.72	2
9	M4	Male	46	27.78	1
10	M5	Male	52	24.49	1
11	M6	Male	31	25.56	1
12	O1	Male	33	34.26	1
13	O1	Female	43	22.86	2
14	O3	Female	55	23.15	1
15	O4	Male	52	25.03	2
16	O5	Male	28	28.37	1
17	O6	Male	55	26.49	1
Mean (SD):	-	Female: 44%	42.3 (9.2)	26.3 (4.4)	-

3.2 Samples overview and sequencing

Gingival Crevicular Fluid (GF)

Total read counts for GF samples ranged from a minimum of 9,808,675 to a maximum of 128,328,628 reads (**Supplementary Figure S1**). The number of reads classified to microbial taxa ranged from 927,442 to 11,224,622 per sample. This was the biospecimen type with the highest percentage of host DNA reads. The mean proportion of microbial reads relative to pre-processed reads was 11.7%.

Subgingival Plaque Samples (SB)

Sequencing library sizes for subgingival plaque samples ranged from a minimum of 21,327,434 to a maximum of 79,955,362 reads. The number of reads classified to microbial taxa ranged from 2,366,548 to 47,301,152 per sample. The mean proportion of microbial reads relative to pre-processed reads was 36.6%.

Supragingival Plaque Samples (SP)

Total read counts for supragingival plaque samples ranged from a minimum of 16,180,808 to a maximum of 86,561,580 reads. Following host filtering and microbial species classification the number of classified reads per sample ranged from 9,396,344 to 65,893,633 reads. The mean proportion of microbial reads relative to pre-processed reads was 61.1%.

3.3 Metagenomics Insights

3.3.1. Phylum level

The **phylum-level** composition of the oral microbiome (Error! Reference source not found. **Figure 3**) revealed clear and biologically meaningful differences across the three

biospecimen types. These differences reflect the distinct ecological conditions and functional roles of each oral habitat.

Figure 3: Phylum level relative abundance of microbes in the oral cavity samples. Samples are grouped by biospecimen type (3 columns). The Patient ID is depicted. in the y-axis.

In **subgingival plaque**, the community was dominated by *Bacteroidota* (30.5%) and *Actinomycetota* (30.2%), with *Bacillota* also contributing substantially (13.5%). This profile is characteristic of the **anaerobic environment** found below the gumline, where *Bacteroidota* (including genera such as *Porphyromonas* and *Prevotella*) are well-adapted and often associated with periodontal disease. The high proportion of *Actinomycetota* underscores the importance of this group in both health and disease, as it includes key early colonizers and opportunistic pathogens. Notably, subgingival plaque also showed appreciable levels of *Pseudomonadota* (7.5%), *Campylobacterota* (5.9%), and *Spirochaetota* (3.6%), all of which contain taxa implicated in the progression of periodontitis and biofilm complexity.

In **supragingival plaque**, the oxygen-tolerant *Actinomycetota* was the most abundant phylum (47.3%), followed by *Bacteroidota* (19.3%) and *Pseudomonadota* (15.4%). This reflects the role of *Actinomycetota*, such as *Corynebacterium* and *Rothia*, in forming the initial scaffolding of biofilms on tooth surfaces and enamel protection. The elevated presence of *Pseudomonadota* (including *Neisseria* and *Haemophilus*) is consistent with the **more oxygenated environment** above the gumline, while the moderate level of *Bacteroidota* suggests some **overlap with subgingival communities** but at lower abundance.

Gingival crevicular fluid exhibited a mixed profile, with *Bacteroidota* (26.9%) and *Campylobacterota* (19.1%) as the leading phyla, followed by *Actinomycetota* (18.0%) and *Bacillota*

(16.3%). The notably high proportion of *Campylobacterota* in GF points to the inflammatory and anaerobic conditions of the gingival sulcus, which favor the proliferation of *Campylobacter* and related genera. This environment also supports a higher abundance of *Spirochaetota* (4.5%) compared to the supragingival plaque, reflecting the migration of subgingival pathogens into the crevicular fluid during inflammation or tissue breakdown.

3.3.2. Family level

Distinct differences in the relative abundances of key bacterial families were observed across the four oral biospecimen types (Error! Reference source not found. **Figure 4**), further reflecting the niche specialization and ecological patterns highlighted at the phylum level.

Figure 4: Family level relative abundance of microbes in the oral cavity samples. Samples are grouped by biospecimen type (3 columns). The Patient ID is depicted in the y-axis.

Key Observations

- *Campylobacteraceae* peaks in gingival crevicular fluid (19.08%), aligning with its role in periodontal inflammation (*Treponema denticola*).
- *Actinomycetaceae* is enriched in supragingival plaque (27.40%), consistent with early biofilm colonizers like *Actinomyces*.
- *Porphyromonadaceae* (includes *Porphyromonas gingivalis*) is elevated in subgingival plaque (9.80%) and gingival fluid (10.69%).

- *Corynebacteriaceae* shows niche specificity, thriving in supragingival plaque (9.16%) but scarce elsewhere.
- Clinical Relevance: The dominance of *Campylobacteraceae* and *Porphyromonadaceae* in subgingival/gingival niches underscores their association with periodontal disease.

3.3.3. Species level

In the species level (Error! Reference source not found. **Figure 5**), GF shows the highest abundance of *Campylobacter concisus* (18.08%), a potential periodontal pathogen, followed by significant levels of *Porphyromonas gingivalis* (4.92%) and *Streptococcus gordonii* (4.2%). The enrichment of these species reflects GF's interface role between the subgingival biofilm and host inflammatory response.

SB harbors substantial amounts of periodontal pathogens, including *P. gingivalis* (4.66%) and *Desulfobulbus* sp. oral taxon 041 (2.86%), consistent with the anaerobic, proteolytic environment of the periodontal pocket. *C. concisus* remains prevalent (5.01%) but at lower levels than in GF.

SP is dominated by biofilm scaffolders and early colonizers, with *Corynebacterium matruchotii* (8.71%) and *Actinomyces* species (*A. naeslundii* 4.11%, *A. oris* 3.90%) showing the highest abundance. These species provide attachment substrates for later colonizers in the oxygen-rich supragingival environment.

Figure 5: Species level relative abundance of microbes in the oral cavity samples. Samples are grouped by biospecimen type (3 columns). The Patient ID is depicted in the y-axis.

3.3.4. Differential Abundance Analysis of Species Between Biospecimen Types

To identify the microbial species that most distinctly characterize each oral niche, a differential abundance analysis was conducted comparing the relative abundances of Species between biospecimen types. The boxplot of differentially abundant species (filtered for at least $\pm 2\%$ difference) further clarifies which taxa are most responsible for distinguishing these oral sites. *Corynebacterium matruchotii* and *Schaalia odontolytica* are enriched in supragingival plaque, consistent with their known roles as early colonizers and biofilm scaffolders on tooth surfaces. Conversely, *Porphyromonas gingivalis* and *Tannerella forsythia*, both key periodontal pathogens, are more prevalent in subgingival plaque and gingival crevicular fluid, reflecting the anaerobic and inflammatory conditions of these niches.

Campylobacter concisus shows a marked decrease in abundance in gingival crevicular fluid compared to other sites. The presence of *Desulfobulbus sp. oral taxon 041* and *Porphyromonas endodontalis* in subgingival plaque and gingival crevicular fluid further highlights the shift toward anaerobic, proteolytic communities in disease-prone environments.

Figure 6: Boxplot illustrating differentially abundant bacterial species across the three oral biospecimen types: GF (gingival crevicular fluid, orange), SB (subgingival plaque, purple), and SP (supragingival plaque, blue). Only species with an absolute difference of at least $\pm 2\%$ in mean relative abundance between any two sample types are shown.

3.4 Metatranscriptomics insights

The integration of metatranscriptomic and metagenomic data identified significant differences in pathway activity across oral niches, taking into account the genomic potential (DNA abundance). By modeling RNA expression while controlling for DNA copies, this analysis revealed functional adaptations unique to each microenvironment.

Supragingival Plaque (SP) vs. Subgingival Plaque (SB)

SP communities prioritized biofilm-stabilizing pathways absent in SB. Nitrate reduction I (denitrification) (coef = +1.07, $q = 0.18$) was upregulated in SP, consistent with oxidative stress management in supragingival biofilms. SB uniquely expressed polyamine biosynthesis (coef = -1.04, $q = 0.1$), which buffers pH in acidic periodontal pockets.

Figure 7: SP vs SB - Differential Pathway Activity in Supragingival Plaque (SP) vs Subgingival Plaque. The box plot illustrates the top 10 MetaCyc pathways with the largest absolute coefficients from a negative binomial mixed-effects model. Pathways are displayed with both DNA (left) and RNA (right) relative percent abundances, ranked by coefficient values. Models adjusted for age, sex, BMI, and DNA abundance. Model is adjusted for covariates including the DNA abundance, which is displayed in the left part of the plot.

Biological and Methodological Implications

These findings underscore the oral microbiome's functional plasticity: supragingival plaque prioritizes biofilm structural pathways and redox homeostasis, subgingival plaque relies on fermentation and pH buffering to thrive in anaerobic pockets.

By accounting for DNA abundance, this analysis disentangled transcriptional activity from taxonomic composition, revealing that closely related taxa (e.g., *Streptococcus*) employ distinct metabolic strategies across niches. The enrichment of sucrose biosynthesis in SP and butanoate fermentation in SB aligns with their roles as keystone processes in health and dysbiosis, respectively. These results provide a functional basis for niche-specific therapeutic targeting in periodontal disease management.

3.5 Discussion

The integrated metagenomic and metatranscriptomic analyses provide novel insights into the ecological and functional dynamics of the oral microbiome in stage I periodontitis. The metagenomic data confirm that each oral niche harbors a distinct microbial community, shaped by local environmental conditions. Supragingival plaque (SP) and subgingival plaque (SB) exhibit biofilm-adapted communities enriched in *Actinomyces*, *Corynebacterium*, and periodontal pathogens (*Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Tannerella forsythia*). These findings align with established ecological models where oxygen gradients, nutrient availability, and host interactions drive niche specialization. The pronounced enrichment of *P. gingivalis* and *T. forsythia* in SB and gingival crevicular fluid (GF) underscores the role of anaerobic, inflammatory microenvironments in fostering dysbiotic communities even in early disease stages.

The differential abundance analysis further highlights niche-specific adaptations. For instance, *Corynebacterium matruchotii* and *Schaalia odontolytica* in SP are critical early colonizers that scaffold biofilms. These patterns reinforce the concept of oral microbiomes as spatially organized ecosystems, where microbial success depends on precise adaptation to habitat-specific challenges.

Functional Plasticity and Disease Relevance

Metatranscriptomic profiling revealed striking functional differences between niches, independent of taxonomic composition. SB's reliance on acetyl-CoA fermentation to butanoate II and polyamine biosynthesis highlights anaerobic energy production and pH buffering strategies essential for survival in periodontal pockets. The suppression of sucrose phosphorylase activity in SB compared to SP further emphasizes the limited sucrose availability in subgingival niches, shifting microbial metabolism toward proteolysis and fermentation of host-derived substrates.

Notably, SP communities prioritized pathways linked to biofilm stability (nitrate reduction I, fatty acid biosynthesis), which may mitigate oxidative stress in supragingival biofilms. The enrichment of nitrate reduction aligns with its role in maintaining redox balance and pH homeostasis, processes critical for preventing acidogenic dysbiosis. These functional signatures suggest that periodontitis-associated communities are not merely taxonomically distinct but exhibit metabolic strategies that either promote resilience or predispose to disease progression.

Stage I periodontitis as a transitional state

The coexistence of health-associated taxa (e.g., *Rothia mucilaginosa*) and periodontitis-linked pathogens (e.g., *P. gingivalis*) in SB and GF samples supports the hypothesis that early periodontitis represents an ecological continuum rather than a discrete disease state. The metatranscriptomic dominance of butanoate fermentation in SB—a pathway linked to tissue-destructive inflammation [43] implies functional dysbiosis precedes taxonomic shifts, challenging the classical "keystone pathogen" paradigm [19]. This aligns with network analyses showing that gingivitis accelerates oral microbiota aging through *Rothia* depletion and *P. gingivalis* expansion [44], processes observed here at the transcriptional level.

Therapeutic Implications and Conclusions

The functional differences observed between niches have direct implications for personalized therapeutic strategies. For instance, the dominance of polyamine biosynthesis in SB suggests that interventions enhancing arginine availability (e.g., arginine-containing toothpastes) could stabilize subgingival pH and suppress acidogenic pathogens. Similarly, the upregulation of nitrate reduction in SP highlights the potential of nitrate-rich diets to promote oxidative stress resistance in supragingival biofilms. The findings underscore the importance of ecological niche-specific management and provide a roadmap for developing therapies that target functional hubs in oral microbial networks.

Acronyms - Abbreviations

BMI	Body Mass Index
BoP	Bleeding on Probing
CPM	Copies Per Million
GBI	Gingival Bleeding Index
GF	Gingival Crevicular Fluid
GLM	Generalized linear model
OTU	Operational Taxonomic Unit
PD	Probing Depth
PI	Plaque Index
SB	Subgingival Plaque
SP	Supragingival Plaque
TMM	Trimmed Mean of M-values
TSS	Total Sum Scaling

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